

CONCEPTUAL BASIS OF FINANCIAL REPORTING**Kholmatova Nodirakhan Quddusovna-****Tashkent Financial Institute Andijan****faculty teacher.****e - mail : nadirahonholmatova74@gmail.com**

Abstract: this article describes the procedure for preparing and submitting financial statements in accordance with International Financial Reporting Standards and its conceptual issues. It contains scientific recommendations on the preparation of financial statements on the basis of IFRS (International Accounting Standard, IAS) and its purpose in ensuring the implementation of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. P Q -4611.

Keywords: concept, financial reporting, international standard principle, balance sheet, profit, loss, assets, capital, liabilities, reporting period.

One of the main advantages of international standards of financial reporting is that it gives international capital markets the opportunity to effectively evaluate and compare the performance of different companies from different countries. This helps companies raise capital efficiently and at low cost, and this is one of the pressing issues of today.

In the review of the literature, O.V. Soloveva, I.A. Chusov, A.E. Larkina and others distinguished two qualitative characteristics, qualitative (basic) and improving, depending on how the conceptual framework affects the usefulness of information:

- main quality features:
 - relevance;
 - fair representation;
- increase quality characteristics:
 - comparability;
 - verifiability (verifiability);
 - timeliness;

- comprehensibility".

The most important issues related to the formation of financial statements are its conceptual basis and the principles of its formation. In our opinion, the main problem is that the conceptual basis of financial reporting is not strictly regulated, because it depends on the rules of reflection in the report of specific objects and business transactions. These situations are causing differences of opinion among economists, and the fact that scholars interpret the principles of reporting and the problems related to them in different ways is due to the existence of certain uncertainties in this regard.

of financial reporting, published by the International Standards Board and replaced by the "Fundamentals of Preparation and Presentation of Financial Reporting" published by the IASB Committee. This Conceptual basis defines the concepts that serve as the basis for the preparation and presentation of financial statements. Therefore, it consists of a system of rules that must be followed by the reporting organization for presenting financial statements to external users. At the same time, the Conceptual Framework also serves to clarify these provisions to the reporting entity, users and other interested parties. and the following addresses the following issues :

- purpose of financial reporting;
- qualitative characteristics of useful financial information;
- definition, recognition and evaluation of the elements that make up the composition of financial statements;
- principles of capital and capital preservation.

It is known that the emergence of any theory is a response to one or another requirement of practice. After all, practice and the experience formed through it are primary compared to theory. Therefore, the theory first aims to satisfy the needs of practice. Undoubtedly, the theory of accounting also arose as a response to the demand of entrepreneurship. As long as this is the case, it would not be wrong to say that accounting theory is really the result of the practice and experience of this field. Even Luco Pacholi, who is considered the founder of the science of accounting, modestly praised his opponents who criticized him in this regard: "I only reflected in the literature what I had in practice" is proof of our opinion.

It is known that any investor and creditor or other lender must make a decision on allocating resources to an enterprise. How users make decisions depends on the expected returns from the investments, in the form of dividends, principal amount, interest payments or appreciation of market prices.

Consequently, the purpose of users is to buy, sell or hold equity and debt instruments and to make decisions about the allocation or extinguishment of loans and other types of debt. Before making a decision, they should have financial information about the entrepreneur they are investing in. Financial information is prepared by the enterprise itself and presented to users.

However, some users are not satisfied with the provided financial information and request other special information from the enterprise that they are interested in (for example, emission prospectuses on securities related to taxation, correspondence with the Government and other regulatory bodies, calculations submitted to statistical authorities, details of certain specific transactions, detailed information about employees) may require. The demands and wishes of such users for information are different, even they are not free from the possibility of conflicting with each other.

We have mentioned above that the board has determined that the enterprise should present a financial report (financial report) intended for general use to users (main users). At the same time, the Conceptual framework also answers the questions about what kind of information this financial report or information about the financial status of the enterprise should have.

The board decided that the financial report should contain two types of information. These are:

- about the economic resources of the enterprise and its requirements;
- information about the impact of operations and other events that cause changes in the economic resources of the enterprise and its requirements.

Both types of information are useful information for users to make decisions about the allocation of resources to the enterprise.

Table 1**Information elements of the financial report**

Information about economic resources (assets) of the enterprise	Information about requirements (obligations) for the enterprise	Information about the impact of transactions and other events that cause changes in the enterprise's economic resources and requirements for it
Conceptually, this information is called information about "the economic phenomena".		

Economic resources and requirements for it: The financial status of any economic entity is determined by its resources, requirements for it, and availability of its net cash flows. Therefore, information about the nature and extent of the reporting entity's economic resources and requirements will help users determine the financial strengths and weaknesses of the reporting entity.

Changes in economic resources and demands: It is true that the financial condition of any economic entity depends on its resources, its demands and the availability of its net cash flows. However, since the economic entity is in continuous activity, the resources available in it and the requirements for it are also in constant movement or change.

the reporting enterprise helps users to understand how much profit the economic resources of this enterprise have brought. This, in turn, indicates how well the management has accomplished its tasks in the rational and efficient use of the company's resources. Information about the volatility and components of this profit is also particularly important in assessing the uncertainty of future cash flows. Usually, information about the financial results of the reporting enterprise in the past periods and the extent to which its management performed its tasks is useful in determining the level of efficiency obtained from the economic resources of the enterprise in the future.

Financial statements are often based on estimates, judgments and models rather than precise descriptions. A conceptual framework defines the rules that underlie these estimates, judgments, and models. These rules represent the objectives to which the Board and companies that prepare financial statements are striving. Like most goals, the Conceptual Framework is far from fully attaining the ideal level of financial reporting, especially in the short term, because it takes time to understand, accept, and apply new methods of analyzing transactions and other events. However, in the quest to improve the usefulness of financial reporting, the determination of the necessary objective is crucial.

Figure 2

Drawing 1. The information system that should be presented in the financial report

It is important to note that this *Conceptual Framework* is not an EMS document and therefore does not set standards for any valuation or disclosure issues. No provision of this *Conceptual Framework* shall prevail over the provisions set forth in any separate MFRS. In some cases, there may be a conflict between *the Conceptual Framework and the MIS*. In this case, the requirements of MHXS prevail over the requirements presented in *the Conceptual Framework*.

The concept serves as a basis for evaluating and developing the currently applicable principles of financial reporting. It is a theoretical basis that determines exactly what events are taken into account, how they are evaluated, and how information is presented in the financial report presented to users for decision-making.

Literature

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